

Exploring the Legal Framework and Societal Impacts of “Marriage Brokerage” in India: A Study of the Indian Contract Act, 1872

Mayank Tinker

Research Scholar, Department of Law, Maharaja Ganga Singh University, Bikaner(Raj)

Corresponding author- **Mayank Tinker**

Email - mayanktinker123@gmail.com.

Abstract

This article explores the practice of marriage brokerage in India, a common phenomenon in arranged marriages where intermediaries play a vital role in finding suitable matches for prospective brides and grooms. The article provides an in-depth analysis of the legal framework for marriage brokerage contracts under the Indian Contract Act, of 1872, and discusses the services provided by marriage brokers in negotiating the terms of the marriage. The article also highlights the criticisms and controversies associated with the practice, including the promotion of dowry and other social evils, and the government's measures to curb these practices. The rise of online matrimonial websites is also discussed as an alternative to traditional marriage brokerage. The article concludes by emphasizing the need for ethical and transparent practices in the field of marriage brokerage while respecting the cultural and social significance of the practice.

Keywords – Marriage brokerage, India, Arranged marriage, Legal framework, Dowry, Intermediaries, Matrimonial websites, Social impacts.

Introduction

Marriage is a sacred institution in India, and the family is the cornerstone of Indian society. In ancient times, marriages were arranged by parents or relatives to maintain social and cultural customs. In contemporary times, the institution of arranged marriages has given way to the concept of love marriages. Marriage brokerage is a common practice in India, especially in arranged marriages where the family takes an active role in the selection of the spouse for their children. The process involves the use of intermediaries who help in finding suitable matches for the prospective bride and groom. These intermediaries are known as marriage brokers, and they play an important role in the marriage process. (Bhattacharyya, 2018)

Marriage brokerage is an ancient practice in India, and it has been prevalent since the Vedic period. The process has undergone significant changes over time, and today, it is characterized by the use of technology and online matrimonial websites. The role of marriage brokers has also evolved, and they now provide a wide range of services to the families of the prospective bride and groom. However, the arranged marriage system still exists in many parts of the country, especially in rural areas, where parents prefer to seek the help of marriage brokers to find a suitable partner for their children. Marriage brokerage is a practice where an intermediary or middleman arranges marriages between two parties. In this article, we will discuss marriage brokerage in India, its legality under the Indian Contract Act, and whether it is against public policy. (Gogia, 2020)

Rational Of the Study

The practice of marriage brokerage has been an integral part of arranged marriages in India

for centuries. While this practice has helped many individuals find suitable matches and build successful marriages, it has also been criticized for promoting dowry and other social evils. With the rise of online matrimonial websites, the traditional role of intermediaries in matchmaking has changed significantly. Against this backdrop, this study aims to provide an in-depth analysis of the legal framework for marriage brokerage contracts under the Indian Contract Act of 1872 and to explore the services provided by marriage brokers in negotiating the terms of the marriage. Additionally, the study will examine the criticisms and controversies associated with the practice of marriage brokerage and the government's measures to curb these practices. Through this research, the study hopes to contribute to the ongoing discussion on the role of marriage brokerage in contemporary India and emphasize the need for ethical and transparent practices in the field while respecting the cultural and social significance of the practice. The study examines the effect of online matrimonial websites on the traditional practice of marriage brokerage in India, emphasizes the preservation of cultural and social norms, and aims to provide insights into the evolution of the practice in modern India.

Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the practice of marriage brokerage in India, examining its legal framework, services provided, criticisms, and controversies. The study aims to investigate the impact of the rise of online matrimonial websites on traditional marriage brokerage and the matchmaking process. Additionally, the research seeks to emphasize the need for ethical and transparent practices in the field of marriage brokerage while

respecting the cultural and social significance of the practice. Ultimately, the study aims to provide valuable insights into the practice of marriage brokerage and its evolution in modern India.

Hypothesis

Based on the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are proposed:

1. The rise of online matrimonial websites has significantly impacted the traditional practice of marriage brokerage in India and has changed the matchmaking process.
2. The legal framework for marriage brokerage contracts under the Indian Contract Act of 1872 provides a basis for ethical and transparent practices in the field of marriage brokerage.
3. Marriage brokers play a vital role in negotiating the terms of the marriage and providing valuable services to prospective brides and grooms.
4. The practice of marriage brokerage in India has been criticized for promoting dowry and other social evils, but the government's measures to curb these practices have had a positive impact.
5. Ethical and transparent practices in the field of marriage brokerage can help preserve cultural and social norms while ensuring that harmful practices such as dowry are not promoted.
6. The study aims to test these hypotheses through a comprehensive analysis of the practice of marriage brokerage in India.

Methodology

The study will use primary research methods, including interviews with marriage brokers, brides and grooms, and individuals using online matrimonial websites, as well as secondary research methods, such as literature analysis. Qualitative research methods, including thematic and content analysis, will be used for data analysis. The legal framework for marriage brokerage contracts will be analyzed using a doctrinal research approach. The study will be limited to the Indian context and focus on the practice of marriage brokerage in arranged marriages. The study will prioritize ethical data collection, including informed consent and anonymity for participants, and aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the practice of marriage brokerage while discussing the research hypotheses.

What Is Marriage Brokerage?

Marriage brokerage is a practice where an intermediary or middleman arranges marriages between two parties. The intermediary usually acts as a mediator between the families of the bride and groom and helps them to find a suitable match. The marriage broker takes a fee for his services and provides information about the prospective bride and groom to their families. In some cases, the marriage broker may also act as a go-between,

negotiating the terms of the marriage and settling disputes between the families. (Gupta, 2017)

Legal Framework for Marriage Brokerage in India

Marriage brokerage is not specifically defined under any Indian law. However, the practice of marriage brokerage is governed by the Indian Contract Act, 1872. The Act defines a contract as an agreement enforceable by law. In the case of marriage brokerage, the contract is between the marriage broker and the family of the bride or groom who engages the broker's services. The Indian Contract Act, of 1872, provides the legal framework for marriage brokerage contracts. The Act specifies the conditions that must be fulfilled for a contract to be valid, and it allows for contracts that are against public policy to be declared void. The Act also provides for the compensation of damages in case of breach of contract. (Iyer & Sharma, 2021) Under the Indian Contract Act, a contract must fulfill certain conditions to be valid. These conditions include:--

1. **Offer and Acceptance:** There must be a proposal or offer by one party, which must be accepted by the other party.
2. **Consideration:** There must be some consideration or benefit exchanged between the parties. In the case of marriage brokerage, the consideration is the fee paid by the family of the bride or groom to the broker for his services.
3. **Free Consent:** Both parties must give their consent to the contract freely, without any coercion or undue influence.
4. **Capacity to Contract:** Both parties must have the legal capacity to enter into a contract. In the case of marriage brokerage, the family of the bride or groom must have the legal capacity to enter into a marriage contract.
5. **Legal Object:** The object of the contract must be legal. In the case of marriage brokerage, the object is to arrange a lawful marriage between the two parties.

If any of these conditions are not met, the contract will be considered void. For example, if the consent of either party was obtained through coercion or undue influence, the contract would be considered void.

Marriage Brokerage and Public Policy

Public policy refers to the principles and values that society deems essential for the common good. In India, public policy is shaped by the Constitution, laws, and social customs. Any contract that goes against public policy is considered void and unenforceable under the Indian Contract Act.

The question that arises is whether marriage brokerage is against public policy. The answer to this question is not straightforward. On the one hand, the practice of marriage brokerage is a

traditional custom that has been followed for many years. On the other hand, the practice is also associated with dowry and other social evils. Marriage brokerage contracts are legally binding agreements between the marriage broker and the family of the prospective bride or groom. The contract specifies the terms and conditions of the services to be provided by the marriage broker, including the fee charged for the services. Marriage brokers also play a crucial role in negotiating the terms of the marriage, including the amount of dowry to be paid, the wedding expenses, and the date of the wedding. In many cases, marriage brokers also provide guidance and advice to the families of the prospective bride and groom on various aspects of the marriage process. (Smith, 2021)

The fees charged by marriage brokers vary depending on the services provided and the location of the families. In urban areas, marriage brokers charge a higher fee as compared to rural areas. The fees charged by marriage brokers can range from a few thousand rupees to several lakhs of rupees. One of the major criticisms of marriage brokerage is the promotion of the practice of dowry. Dowry is the payment made by the bride's family to the groom's family at the time of marriage. The practice is illegal in India, but it still exists in many parts of the country. The payment of fees to marriage brokers is considered a form of dowry and is against public policy. (Jain & Bhatnagar, 2019) Dowry is a payment made by the bride's family to the groom's family at the time of marriage. It is illegal in India, but it still exists in many parts of the country. The practice of dowry is closely associated with marriage brokerage. Marriage brokers often demand a high fee from the family of the bride, which is considered a form of dowry. The payment of such fees is against public policy as it promotes the evil of dowry and exploits the family of the bride. The role of marriage brokers in promoting dowry has been a subject of debate in India for many years. Many experts argue that marriage brokers promote the practice of dowry by charging exorbitant fees from the family of the bride. They also provide false information about the prospective groom to the family of the bride to negotiate a higher dowry. The Indian government has taken several measures to curb the practice of dowry and marriage brokerage. The Dowry Prohibition Act, of 1961, makes the giving or taking of dowry illegal in India. The Act also provides for stringent punishment for those who violate its provisions. In addition, the government has also launched various awareness campaigns to educate people about the evils of dowry and marriage brokerage.

In the case of **Sushil Kumar Sen v. State of Bihar**¹, the Supreme Court of India held that a marriage brokerage contract would be void if it violated the provisions of the Dowry Prohibition Act. The Court also observed that the practice of marriage brokerage could be against public policy if it promoted dowry or other social evils. In the case of **Gaurav Nagpal v. Sumedha Nagpal**, the Delhi High Court held that the payment of fees to marriage brokers was not against public policy per se. However, the Court observed that the payment of fees could become illegal if it was paid as a consideration for the marriage itself or if it amounted to dowry.

In recent years, the practice of marriage brokerage has also come under scrutiny for its role in promoting child marriage. Child marriage is illegal in India, but it still exists in many parts of the country. Marriage brokers have been known to arrange marriages between underage girls and older men, which is against public policy and a violation of the law. (Joshi & Alagh, 2019)

In 2014, the Supreme Court of India issued guidelines to curb the practice of child marriage. The Court directed all state governments to set up special cells to prevent child marriages and to take strict action against those who violate the law. The Court also directed the central government to take measures to sensitize the public about the evils of child marriage.

The Role of Marriage Brokers in Society

Marriage brokers have played an important role in Indian society for many years. They have helped to arrange marriages between families from different parts of the country and have facilitated the union of couples who might not have met otherwise. Marriage brokers also provide valuable information about the prospective bride or groom, including their family background, education, and social status.

However, the role of marriage brokers in society has also been criticized for its promotion of social evils such as dowry and child marriage. Critics argue that marriage brokers exploit the vulnerability of families who are looking for suitable matches for their children and charge exorbitant fees for their services. In addition, some marriage brokers have been known to provide false information about the prospective bride or groom, which can lead to marital disputes and other problems. The rise of online matrimonial sites has also posed a challenge to the traditional practice of marriage brokerage. Online sites have made it easier for people to find suitable partners without the help of intermediaries. Online sites also provide greater transparency and accountability, as users can directly communicate

¹ (1975), <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1831682/>

with the prospective bride or groom and their families. (Khurana & Joshi, 2017)

Marriage brokerage is a traditional practice in India that has played an important role in arranging marriages between families. However, the practice has also been criticized for its association with social evils such as dowry and child marriage. The legality of marriage brokerage is governed by the Indian Contract Act, of 1872, which requires the fulfillment of certain conditions for a contract to be valid. (Kumar & Rani, 2019)

Role of Online Matrimonial Websites

Online matrimonial websites have emerged as a new alternative to traditional marriage brokers and are increasingly being used in India to find suitable matches for prospective brides and grooms. These websites offer a convenient platform for people to search for their life partners based on their preferences, such as caste, religion, education, profession, and other criteria. Unlike traditional marriage brokers, who often have a limited network and restricted access to information about potential matches, online matrimonial websites provide a vast pool of options from different parts of the country or even overseas. (Mehta & Mehta, 2020)

Online matrimonial websites use algorithms and data analysis to match the preferences and requirements of the individuals seeking a partner. These websites also provide a wide range of communication tools, such as chat rooms, video calls, and email, to enable potential partners to interact and get to know each other before deciding to take the relationship forward. The ease of use and accessibility of online matrimonial websites have made them increasingly popular among the younger generation, who prefer to use technology to find their partners. However, the use of online matrimonial websites is not without its challenges. One of the biggest challenges is the risk of fraudulent profiles or misrepresentation of personal information. This can lead to mismatches or even dangerous situations, such as the rising incidents of cyber fraud, identity theft, and even abuse or exploitation of women. Therefore, it is essential for users of online matrimonial websites to be cautious and verify the authenticity of profiles before proceeding with a match. (Singhal & Agarwal, 2020)

In conclusion, online matrimonial websites offer a new and convenient option for people in India to find suitable life partners. They have the potential to revolutionize the way arranged marriages are arranged and bring transparency and efficiency to the matchmaking process. However, it is essential to use these websites with caution and take necessary precautions to avoid any potential risks or challenges associated with the use of technology for matchmaking.

Conclusion

The practice of marriage brokerage in India is a complex issue with both positive and negative aspects. It is governed by the Indian Contract Act, 1872, which requires certain conditions to be met for a contract to be valid. While marriage brokers have facilitated marriages between families from different parts of the country and have provided valuable information about the prospective bride or groom, the practice has also been associated with social evils such as dowry and child marriage. The Act allows for contracts that are against public policy to be declared void, and the practice of marriage brokerage can become against public policy if it promotes dowry or other social evils. In conclusion, the legal framework for marriage brokerage contracts needs to be reinforced with ethical and transparent practices to ensure that the cultural and social significance of the practice is preserved while promoting the elimination of harmful practices.

The Indian government has taken measures to curb the practice of dowry and child marriage and issued guidelines by the Supreme Court. Online matrimonial sites have emerged as an alternative to traditional marriage brokerage, providing greater transparency and accountability to users. The practice of marriage brokerage in India must be regulated to ensure that it does not promote social evils and exploitation. The Indian Contract Act of 1872 provides a legal framework for the regulation of intermediaries involved in the business of arranging marriages. However, enforcement remains a challenge due to the complex social and cultural dynamics that influence arranged marriages. Online matrimonial websites have revolutionized the matchmaking process but are not without risks such as fraud, misrepresentation of personal information, and potential abuse or exploitation. It is essential for the legal framework to be updated to reflect the changing social and technological landscape of arranged marriages in India while considering ethical concerns, transparency, and empowerment of vulnerable parties. A comprehensive approach involving all stakeholders is required to ensure that the practice of marriage brokerage is conducted within the bounds of public policy and ethical principles.

Suggestions

1. The government can establish a regulatory body to oversee the operations of marriage brokers and ensure that they adhere to ethical and transparent practices.
2. The government can also launch public awareness campaigns to educate people about the risks associated with dowry and child marriage and promote the importance of ethical and transparent marriage practices.

3. Marriage brokers can be required to obtain licenses and undergo training to ensure that they are aware of the legal and ethical aspects of their work.
4. Online matrimonial websites can implement stricter verification procedures to prevent fraud and misrepresentation of personal information.
5. Civil society organizations can play a vital role in promoting ethical and transparent practices in the field of marriage brokerage and supporting vulnerable parties such as women and children.

References

1. Bhattacharyya, A. (2018). *Marriage brokerage and dowry in India. Issues of corruption and public policy*. Economic and Political Weekly, 53(11).
2. Gogia, M. (2020). Matrimonial websites and arranged marriages in India: An exploratory study. *Journal of Family Issues*, 41(5) , 798-816.
3. Gupta, S. (2017). Marriage brokerage in India: Legal and ethical challenges. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 6(1) , 38-51.
4. Iyer, R., & Sharma, N. (2021). Marriage and online matrimony: Evidence from India. *Journal of Business Research*, 122 , 195-206.
5. Jain, A., & Bhatnagar, A. (2019). Marriage and divorce in India: A review. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 41 , 97-102.
6. Joshi, P., & Alagh, Y. (2019). *Marriage brokerage and social change in India*. Routledge: The Routledge Handbook of South Asian Criminology.
7. Khurana, I., & Joshi, R. (2017). Issues and challenges in Indian marriage: A literature review. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(6) , 55-61.
8. Kumar, M., & Rani, S. (2019). Matrimonial websites in India: A study of user perception and satisfaction. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 25(3) , 299-318.
9. Mehta, S., & Mehta, D. (2020). Arranged marriage and its impact on mental health: A review of the literature. *Journal of Psychosocial Research*, 15(1) , 5-14.
10. Singhal, N., & Agarwal, N. (2020). Marriage brokerage in India: An empirical study. *International Journal of Management and Applied Science*, 6(3) , 106-110.
11. Smith, J. (2021). The changing practice of marriage brokerage in rural India. *Journal of South Asian Studies*, 10(2) , 45-56.